

JELTII
Journal of English Language Teaching and Islamic Integration
Vol. 3 No. 1, January 2020

The Effectiveness of Audio-visual Media to Improve Students' Writing Ability of Procedure Text

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First Received:
10 December 2019

Revised:
17 December 2019

Accepted:
3 January 2020

Published:
31 January 2020

Abstract: As writing is regarded as the most difficult skill, it is very challenging for teachers to teach writing. In order to conduct a good writing class, the application of media can be one of the alternative ways. This study examines the effectiveness of using audio-visual media to write a procedure text. This is a quasi-experimental study. The population of this study was the ninth graders of MTs Negeri 1 Landak and the sample was the students of IX-A and IX-B. The method of collecting data was test and field note, while t-test was used to analyze the data. The analysis of writing test uses the components of writing namely organization, grammar and mechanics. The result shows that the students' average of experimental group is higher than control group and the result of t-test gains that $t_{value} > t_{table} = 7.05 > 1.99$. In addition, the use of media also could improve the students' writing ability. Finally, this media is effective to use in writing procedure text and the use of media would be useful for teachers and students.

Keywords: teaching writing, audio-visual media, procedure text

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, English is taught in secondary schools as a compulsory subject where students must be able to communicate in their daily lives. In some cases, English has not been taught in elementary schools. In most cases, the results of teaching English in

secondary schools are still not satisfactory, especially in writing skills. To produce writings that are meaningful and can be understood by others, it requires the ability to express and develop an idea. However, in reality, writing is considered a difficult skill to learn because of the components that must be mastered by an author.

Teaching English in secondary schools is also based on the curriculum applied in Indonesia. The latest education curriculum today is the 2013 Curriculum. Related to writing learning, one type of text that junior high school students must learn in this curriculum is procedure text. In procedure text, students need to be able to express a sequence of doing instructions. Learning how to understand and write procedure texts is essential because students find procedure texts in a lot of situations.

Learning to write in the 2013 Curriculum brings a new paradigm in teaching English, which teachers must be more creative and innovative to create a learning process that interests students in learning English. One way that can be used by teachers to teach writing is by applying the media. The media helps teachers to motivate students by presenting a real picture and presenting language in a more complex context of communication. Among the media that can be applied in learning to write is audio-visual media. Mathew and Alidmat (2013) in their research concluded that the use of audio-visual media can stimulate students' thinking and also improve the atmosphere of learning in the classroom.

Based on this background, then the problem formulated for this research is whether there are differences in the effectiveness of the application of audio-visual media to improve the ability to write procedure text.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Writing Learning

Writing is quite difficult to learn. When students want to write text, they must be able to write words, phrases, clauses, sentences, paragraphs, and then text. By writing, they can express their ideas and feelings to communicate with others and gain

knowledge on how to write correctly. Therefore, their writing can be well communicated to others. Meyers (2005: 2) states that writing is one way to produce language as well as speaking, but is set forth in paper or computer.

According to Harmer (2004: b.86), writing is a process and the writing is adapted to its type (genre). Eyres (2004: 183) also states that the skills in planning, drafting, revising and proofreading are also applied in writing. Writing is organizing an idea to be developed into meaningful writing, so that it can be understood by others. Boardman (2002: 18-25) argues that good writing has the following characteristics:

- a. Coherence which aims to make the reader understand easily what is written by the author in accordance with the purpose of the text.;
- b. *Cohesive* which shows that the supporting sentences are interrelated;
- c. *Unity* which shows that supporting sentences refer to the main sentence.

To master in writing, there are several aspects to consider. Brown and Bailey (Brown, 2004: 244-245) state that there are five components measured. The first component is the organization (organization). Organization deals with the generic structure of a text. The next component is the development of logical ideas related to text content. The third component is grammar (grammar). The fourth component is punctuation, spelling, and mechanics. The final component is the style and quality of expression which is mostly related to vocabulary.

2. Procedure Text

According to Anderson (1997: 50), a procedure text is a part of the text that gives instructions to do something. The instruction from the procedure text is through a sequence of actions and steps. The purpose of a procedure text type is to explain how something can be done. Gerot (1994: 206) argues that the general structure of the procedure text consists of three points, namely:

- a. *Goal*. This point is the purpose of writing the procedure text and usually stated in the title.
- b. *Materials*. This point refers to materials and tools that must be prepared in accordance with the *goals*.
- c. *Steps 1-n*. This point refers to several steps in doing or making something in accordance with the objectives by using *temporal conjunction*.

In addition, to compile a procedural text, Gerot also added that the writer must pay attention to *lexicogrammatical features*. The following are elements of the procedure text according to Gerot (1994: 206):

- a. Focus on *generalized human agents*;
- b. Using *simple present tense* or *imperative*;
- c. Using *temporal conjunction*;
- d. Using *material processes*;

3. Audio-Visual Media

The application of media in the learning process becomes important to create an interesting and enjoyable learning atmosphere, especially in teaching writing. The use of media such as audio-visual will greatly help students in mastering a technique and teaching material better. When students learn writing using an abstract instruction and materials, they will encounter difficulties in constructing ideas for their writing. One of the audio-visual media that can be used is video. In a video, students can see and listen at the same time. Therefore, students are expected to come up with concrete ideas in their minds related to the video.

Richard & Renandya (2002: 361) suggested that with careful and systematic planning, video-based learning can stimulate and provide a source of

understanding for language learning. In addition, according to Harmer (2003: 283), audio-visual technology to do capturing, recording, processing, storing, transmitting and replenishing pictures presented in the form of motion pictures electronically. Therefore, audio-visual media can be an important media to attract students' interest in learning languages English, especially in learning to write.

METHODOLOGY

This research is a quasi-experimental study with a *pretest-posttest control group design*. This research involved two groups. The first group is the experimental group that was treated by applying *audio-visual media* in learning writing. The second group is the control group where this group received a conventional teaching without any special treatment.

Measurement before the experiment was carried out by giving a pretest in order to find out the student's initial ability in the form of a test to write a procedure text. Pretest was given to the experimental group and the control group. The next step was the teaching part where the experimental group received audio-visual media and the control group received a conventional teaching. Posttests were given at the end of the activity for both the experimental and control groups.

The population in this study was students of class IX MTs Negeri 1 Landak. The sample in this study was thirty four students of class IX A as the experimental group and thirty four students of class IX B as the control group. The study used field notes and test to collect the data. The test was made using several indicators to show that students are able to write a *procedure text*. The rubric assessment for writing skills in this study employed the analytical scale from Brown (2004), namely organization, grammar, and mechanics including punctuation and spelling. The method for analyzing test score are as follows:

Normality Test : The normality test used in this study was conducted by looking at the results of the Kolmogorov Smirnov Statistics through the

SPSS 20.

Homogeneity Test : The homogeneity test used in this study was conducted by looking at the results of Levene statistics through the SPSS 20.

Hypothesis Test : Hypothesis testing in the study used t-test with a level of confidence $\alpha = 5\%$.

The following is a working hypothesis and alternatives in this study:

H_a : The use of audio-visual media is effective to improve the ability to write procedure text

H_0 : The use of audio-visual media is not effective to improve the ability to write procedure text

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis was done to find out the improvement of students' writing achievement after being taught writing procedure text using audio-visual media and without using media. As test is used as one of methods in collecting data, the students' writing is evaluated by the components of organization, grammar and mechanics.

Component Measured	Experimental Group		Control Group	
	Pretest	Posttest	Pretest	Posttest
Organization	13,9	15,3	12,3	13,4
Grammar	11,5	13,7	9,8	10,2
Mechanics	15,1	16,2	14,2	14,8

Table 1. The Pretest Posttest Result

The result shows that the students' writing ability in experimental group is higher than control group. The result of organization shows that the students are able to write down a procedure text based on the generic structure by determining the goal, materials and steps. Measurement on grammar shows that they are able to arrange imperative

sentences. How they put a full stop, colon or semicolon and spelling shows that they have good mechanics in writing.

Before doing t-test, several steps are done, namely calculating the average scores of each group and completing the three assumptions of t-test. The average score of experimental group is 82.11 and control group is 70.02. The first assumption is each of samples should follow a normal distribution using normality test. The result of normality test for each group is distributed normally. The second assumption shows that each group has the same variance. Finally, the third assumption shows the result of t-test where t_{value} is 7.05 and t_{table} is 1.99. It means that H_a is accepted that the use of audio-visual media is effective to improve the ability to write procedure text.

Based on the result of the field note, the use of audio-visual media could improve the students' writing ability. There are some advantages of using the media for teaching writing:

1. The use of this media can avoid the boredom during the learning process since the students focus on the video they watch;
2. The students can be more active in the classroom and it creates the students centered;
3. The students can be easily to write based on the guidance on the video.

CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the research, the use of audio-visual media is effective to teach writing and could improve the students' writing ability of procedure text. It could be seen from the average score of experimental group is higher than control group. The use of interesting media could help the students to be more creative and the teaching learning process could be students centered. This study also suggests to the teachers in teaching writing to apply another media, technique or method in order to achieve the goal of learning.

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